

Anomaly Detection using Machine Learning Models in Water Supply Systems

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Abstract — Water loss remains a critical global concern, particularly within the present-day scarcity of water resources. This problem constitutes a significant challenge faced by water supply systems (WSS) utilities, as these deal with water leakage, which can persist undetected for extended periods of time and have a significant impact on the system efficiency. The occurrence of water leakage in these systems can range from 3% to over 50% depending on the level of system network maintenance performed, since it happens in pipe and/or junctions by uncontrolled actions [1]. Moreover, and according to the Portuguese regulator ERSAR in the RASARP 2024 [2], actual water leakage in Portugal in 2023 was 5.5 m³/(km day) for the bulk side, which corresponds to a loss of more than 21 billion m³/year. On the other hand, on the distribution side the value was 2.4 m³/(km day) representing 4.6 billion m³/year. To address this problem, several leakage management measures can be implemented, including preventive measures, detection and localization techniques, and repair initiatives. The detection and localization techniques comprise hardware- and software-based methods, which can integrate Machine Learning (ML) models and digital twins technologies. This data analytics integration can become a powerful tool in automated data analysis and hydraulic simulation, leading to significant advancements to a faster and more accurate leakage detection and localization.

This work aims to present a novel sub-framework employing ML techniques to detect anomalies in pressure time series, as small discrepancies in the values may represent potential water leakage scenarios in the water system. This approach is implemented on a benchmark dataset, the BattLeDIM network [3], in which different ML-based models were evaluated and then compared with prior baseline results.

Keywords — Water Leakage, Water Supply System, Machine Learning, Anomaly Detection, BattLeDIM Benchmark

TOPIC

2) b.: Technologies for the Wellbeing - Innovative Technologies for Smart Cities".

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